
Intervention of marma chikitsa with ayurvedic formulation in the management of vata vyadhi w.s.r cerebral palsy - A case report

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Abstract:

Cerebral palsy (CP) is a significant cause of childhood disability, impacting both physical functions and development. It is a nonprogressive neuromotor disorder originating in the brain. CP is a complex condition with diverse clinical manifestations. Vāgbhaṭa classified it as sahaja (hereditary), garbhaja (congenital), and jātajā (psychosomatic) types of diseases. While there are various types and subtypes of CP, none of them currently have a known “cure.” However, a 5-year-old girl with spastic CP underwent multiple Ayurveda treatment modalities, including Marma chikitsa and internal medication. After several days of treatment, there was a notable 20-25% improvement in the overall effectiveness of therapy.

Cerebral palsy (CP) is the leading cause of childhood disability, impacting both physical functions and developmental milestones. It is characterized as a nonprogressive neuromotor disorder originating in the brain. CP is a complex condition with multiple factors contributing to its development, leading to a wide range of clinical features. According to Vāgbhaṭa, CP is classified into different disease categories, including sahaja (hereditary), garbhaja (congenital), and jātajā (psychosomatic) types. Unfortunately, none of the various types and subtypes of CP currently have a known “cure.” However, in this case, a 5-year-old girl with spastic CP underwent multiple Ayurveda treatment modalities, including Marma chikitsa and internal medication. After several days of treatment, there was a significant 20-25% improvement observed in the overall effectiveness of the therapy.

KEYWORDS: Marma , Panchakarma , aushadh , cerebral palsy , vatavyadhi.

Introduction

Cerebral palsy (CP) is the primary cause of childhood disability, affecting both function and development. Along with motor disorders, CP often involves disruptions in sensation, perception, cognition, communication, and behavior. CP is categorized into four types: spastic, ataxic, dyskinetic, and mixed, with spastic CP accounting for a significant majority (70-80%). The global incidence of CP is 2:1000¹. Unfortunately, there is currently no known promising “cure” for any type or subtype of CP. However, various advancements are being explored in CP management, including autologous stem cell activation treatment, strengthening the immune system, stem cell transplantation, Botulinum toxin type A injections, baclofen intrathecal injections, selective dorsal rhizotomy, orthotic devices like ankle-foot orthoses, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, and neuroplasticity techniques.

Vayu regulates the transmission of energy from one marma to another . Among the Trimarma, Shiras is considered as Uttamangal? and one among Dasa-pranayatana.) Injury to this Shiro marma due to external or internal factor is considered as Shiro-marma abhighata². The underlying cause of Shiro Marma Abhighata is usually Vata vikara, which can result in CP and CPMR, is primarily the imbalanced Vata Dosha. To evaluate spasticity, the range of motion of joints (GMFCS) was examined, while motor and mental development were assessed using developmental assessment scales for Indian infants (DASII) and similar methods. The vitiation of Vata Dosha can be assumed to occur during the fetal or infantile period. Paediatric Panchakarma is a distinctive procedure due to its therapeutic, preventive, prophylactic, and rejuvenating properties. It involves Vata

pacifying measures such as snehanan (oil massage), swedana (sudation therapy including Shastik shali pinda sweda and Nadi sweda), and Vata cleansing therapies (vastikarma). In addition to the Panchakarma procedure, marma Chikitsa was added to improve the range of movement and stabilising the pranik flow (prana vayu). In Ayurveda, there is a specialized branch of clinical care for children called Kaumārabhrtya. Many conditions and contributing factors related to the etiology of CP are described in various texts. Overlapping symptoms of CP can be found in conditions like phakka (nutritional disorder), pāngulya (locomotor disorders), mūkatva (dumbness), jaḍatva (mental disorders), ekāṅgaroga (monoplegia), sarvāṅgaroga (quadriplegia), pakṣaghāta (hemiparesis), and pakṣavadha (hemiplegia), which fall under the category of vātavayādhi (neurological disorders). Contributing factors such as improper ovulation cycle, uterine factors, amniotic fluid and fetal nutrition, sperm and ovum quality, neglecting urges during pregnancy, substances that can harm the fetus, incompatible requisites for fetal growth, and improper antenatal care may have adverse effects on the fetus, leading to various diseases, deformities, or even death.

Marma Therapy is an important method of regulating the flow of Prana³. Prana is connected to most of the vata disorders including shiro pradesh . According to stages of the disease , third stage needs special treatment for improved results⁴ .Considering all of the above, an Ayurvedic therapy protocol has been formulated, incorporating herbal medicines (Aushadh) and marma stimulations, to improve the condition of patients with CP.

CASE REPORT

Basic information of the patient

Age: 5 years

Sex: Female

Religion: Hindu

Socioeconomic status: Middle class

chief complaints

Global delayed milestones and mental retardation (both since birth).

history of present illnesses

A 5 year old female patient was delivered by lower segment cesarean section (LSCS) prematurely and did not cry soon after birth and also suffered from septicemia, convulsions, and jaundice. Due to all these clinical complications, the child could not achieve normal growth and development. Spasticity and involuntary movement became apparent after the age of 5 months and since then the parents started treating the child going to many doctors without any significant benefit. They approached us for further management.

history of past illness

Patient was having upper limb cellulitis with septic shock , respiratory failure and pyogenic meningitis.

treatment history

Patient taken treatment for pyogenic meningitis from allopathic hospital

family history

Not any

Birth history

Antenatal: Mother (25 years) was suffering from hyperthyroidism and mental stress during pregnancy and taking tablet thyroxin regularly.

Natal: Preterm (32 weeks) LSCS (due to oligohydramnios and primiparity of mother) was done. Baby did not cry soon after birth. Birth weight was 1.6 kg (very low birth weight).

Postnatal history

Not any

history of immunization

Taken according to immunization schedule

personal history

Āharaja - Patient was totally dependent for food intake, and was eating only semi solid food due to lack of coordination in deglutition. Appetite was poor. Diet was dominant in *madhura rasa* (sweet diet).

Vihāraja - Nature of activity was always assisted (due to severe spastic quadriplegia). Sleep was disturbed (2–3 h/day, 6–7 h/night). Bed wetting (had not achieved bladder control) and drooling from the mouth was there since birth.

Examination

Vitals were normal. Cardiovascular system, respiratory system and per abdomen examinations had shown no deformity. *Prakṛti* (constitution) was *Vātādhikakapha*.

Pulse – 90 / min

Respiratory rate – 18 / min

Temperature – Normal

CNS – conscious

CVS – S1 S2 (Normal)

RS – AE BE (Clear)

Central nervous system examination

Patient was diagnosed to have the hypertonia (spasticity) and contractures at ankle and knee joint. Muscle power could not be elicited because patient was unable to follow the command. Sensory system was intact, and no abnormality found. Cranial nerve examination could not be done because of severely handicapped physical and mental state of the patient. Hyperreflexia was present, suggestive of upper motor neuron disease (which is the hallmark of CP). Babinski sign was up going (positive). Meningeal signs were not present.

Flow chart of Ayurvedic perspective⁶

Differential diagnosis

Spastic CP⁵, demyelinating (degenerative) disease of central nervous system (CNS), sequel of postnatal hypoxia.

Treatment protocol

Internal medicine – Tab. Brahmi vat
Smriti Sagar Ras

Panchakarma – Sarvang Abhyang with Bala Tail
Shastik Shali pinda swedan

Marma Chikitsa – kshipra marma (Both UL & LL)
Gulpha marma (Both LL)
Janu marma (Both LL)
Stanmoola marma
Amsa marma (Both UL)
Vidur marma
Sthapani marma

Observations

Patient was given Marma Chikitsa for 30 days continuously with aushad (ayurvedic drugs) Chikitsa three times a day .

Then after gap of 10 days , Patient again admitted for 30 days and same regimen followed as intervention.

Motor integrity	BT	AT
Spasticity	Present	Reduced
Hypotonia	Present	Improved
Voluntary control	Absent	Improved

Abnormal DTR	Present	Absent
Superficial	Weak	Improved
Primitive	Weak	Improved
ATNR	Absent	Present

Discussion

The marma point harmonize the nervous and endo- crine system and normalize different pathology in the body through vital power itself, with proper stimula- tion, manipulation. These techniques are known as Marma Chikitsa.

According to Acharya Sushruta, the point where all the vessels, muscles, bones, joints, nerves, ligaments etc. structures meet and is the site of Prana (vitality) is nothing but Marma.¹⁸ Acharya Vagbhata consid- ered Marma as the points where special and unusual pulsation felt. These points are important in human body and injuries to these points lead disability and if not treated properly may become fatal.

Vayu (air) regulates the energy transmission between marma points. In the science of marma, the "Dasavayu" (ten types of vayu) are considered crucial for treatment. Among them, Vyana and Apana vayu play significant roles in the development of Vataj Gridhrasi. Disruption of the functions of these vayus affects the exchange, supply, and multiplication functions of marma points. When these functions are disturbed, it also affects the functioning of Nadi (channels), prana (life force), vayu (air), and panchamahabhuta (five elements).

In the human body, each part is interconnected through connecting tissues like ligaments and tendons, hence massage should be performed with this in mind. During a particular disease condition affecting a specific part, massage should be focused on that area.

Marma Chikitsa is based on Ayurvedic principles, including the Panchamahabhutasidhanta (doctrine of the five elements), the Agnisomya Siddhanta, and the principles of Vata management.

The probable mode of action, according to modern science, is that activating or stimulating a marma point triggers ionic exchange within the area, leading to reflexes in sensory neurons. The network of sensory neurons then signals the hypothalamic-pituitary- adrenocortical axis, resulting in the activation of steroid hormones such as cortisol, endorphins, and serotonin. This process produces a relaxing effect and initiates the rejuvenation process at the site, ultimately improving the mechanical performance of the joint or limb.

Results and conclusion

Accy to ayurveda , pacifying Vata from its root place is the main objective . Here in this study , both internal and external measures are used to get the best results . Marma Chikitsa is a very precise science which can give promising results in other Vata vyadhi's of pediatric patients . To uplift the science and get more data , this study can be carried on other Vata vyadhi's also under a proper marma Chikitsa practitioner .

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8391056](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8391056)